

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Deep Learning for Ore Haulage Monitoring: Vibrational Analysis Using a VGG16 Network

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ABSTRACT Automated detection of work cycles in underground ore haulage is crucial for optimizing operational efficiency and minimizing costs, yet existing methods often rely on manual logging or basic telematics, which can be inefficient and prone to errors. This study addresses this gap by presenting a novel approach that utilizes IMU sensor mounted on haul trucks to accurately estimate ore haulage cycles. By collecting data from various work shifts, we analyzed 1473 unique ore haulage cycles across various machines and environments, demonstrating the robustness of our method. The proposed solution incorporates advanced deep learning models, specifically VGG16 and autoencoders, to process the sensor data and detect cycles effectively. Our approach not only enhances real-time tracking of truck operations but also enables better route planning and load management, thereby reducing idle time. The model achieved an accuracy of approximately 87%, validating its effectiveness as an easy to implement solution for work cycle detection in the challenging conditions of underground mines. This automation facilitates continuous optimization by providing valuable insights into operational performance, contributing to improved long-term productivity. The findings indicate that leveraging IMU sensor data through machine learning techniques presents a significant advancement in the field of ore haulage cycle detection, ultimately benefiting the mining industry by enhancing efficiency and reducing operational costs.

INDEX TERMS Work cycles detection, ore haulage, IMU, VGG16, autoencoders, underground mining, operational efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wheeled transport is crucial in underground mining, serving as the backbone of horizontal material movement. Haul trucks and wheel loaders are among the most costly machines, and their efficiency significantly impacts blasting, transport, and processing operations. Optimizing these machines in terms of downtime, reliability, and productivity is critical, leading to a need for proactive measures and tools for improved planning and organization [10], [23].

Developing monitoring systems in harsh mining environments and extensive infrastructures faces challenges such as social resistance and high costs. Despite these hurdles, performance monitoring is essential for managing fleets and production under changing conditions, as well as for

equipment exploitation and planning. Accurate planning requires estimating production potential, considering factors like mining face height, ore thickness, ventilation, equipment availability, haulage capacity, seismic measures, and blasting feasibility [11], [25].

Detecting operational components enhances situational awareness by identifying various regimes and investigating factors like downtime, wear, and fuel efficiency. For instance, a study in [4] optimized loader fuel consumption by adjusting bucket trajectories, resulting in a 30% reduction in fuel use. Another study [26] utilized IMU data from haul trucks to detect turning moments and assess dynamic overloads on joints. Extended research in [25] analyzed long-term data from 19 machines, identifying factors linked to higher failure rates in specific mining areas. Additionally, a method for diagnosing ore transport issues was proposed in [17], using machine learning on truck travel time data to monitor route

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conditions and improve fleet management. Similar work in [24] employed vehicle speed, gear, and accelerometer signals to recognize haulage cycles and evaluate road surface quality.

Performance parameters for loading and hauling machines are critical, including driving speed (both loaded and unloaded), operational restrictions, loading capacity, and loading/unloading times, and are often based on catalogue data [3]. These operations are cyclical: loading, driving with load, unloading, and returning empty. No single parameter captures the entire haulage process, as signal observations often display atypical behavior, with statistical properties changing over time [9]. Operational regimes may consist of multiple coexisting processes, marked by critical transition points where behaviors change significantly. Therefore, time series segmentation is essential, dividing observations into homogeneous segments [27].

Various approaches for detecting or estimating ore haulage work cycles have emerged in recent literature. In [29], a model combining K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was introduced to recognize subprocesses in wheel loader cycles, achieving an impressive 99.4% accuracy using hydraulic, transmission, and operator action data. Study [15] presented a solution for detecting excavator work cycles through IMUs on key machine parts. Additionally, [13] proposed an algorithm for detecting haul truck unloading based on engine and breaking signals, highlighting the limitations of hydraulic sensors. Similar work was conducted in [8], where DBSACN combined with SVM was utilized for this task. In [14], a virtual sensor model using multiple data sources was created to overcome the limitations of hydraulic sensors. A method for detecting ore cycles for loaders based on hydraulic sensors was also reported in study [12], yielding good results. Neural networks for haul truck cycle recognition were explored in [22], while [28] focused on optimizing wheel loader cycles, revealing productivity and fuel efficiency differences of up to 300% and 150% among operators, respectively.

Data on operational regimes can significantly enhance production forecasting in mining. In [5], six machine learning algorithms—random forest, SVM, MLP, CART, k-nearest neighbors, and M5Tree—were tested for haul truck production estimation using IoT data. Key variables identified for process improvement included start/end times and intervals between operations. In [7], three neural network models (BPNN, ELM, BRNN) combined with a Gaussian mixture model were applied to predict truck performance, revealing haul distance as the most influential variable. Research in [1] utilized safety system data to simulate mining transport, while [6] focused on machine learning to predict driving times, improving scheduling and performance.

In this paper, we propose a method for estimating ore haulage cycles using data from inertial measurement units (IMUs) mounted on haul trucks. Our approach employs deep learning techniques, including VGG16 and autoencoders,

achieving an accuracy of 87.73% and a recall of 95.66%, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and reducing costs in underground mining operations. This article is structured as follows: Section II outlines the materials and methods used in our study, Section III presented the results and their analysis, and Section IV discusses the implications of our findings and concludes the paper.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the materials and methods used to develop and validate the proposed IMU-based monitoring system for haul truck efficiency. It details the data collection process, the algorithms employed, and the training process of developed models. All of below stated research was created with the use of Python language, especially the PyTorch framework [18] where focus was put on neural networks.

A. DATA COLLECTION AND PREPARATION

The data in this research was collected as part of Nethelix project [16], during which various experiments were held on the machinery in underground mines for the task of operational optimization. During this period, hundreds of work hours of underground haul trucks operation was recorded using IMU sensors mounted on different machines in various parts of the mines. In each recording session, one NGIMU sensor (The Next Generation IMU made by x-io Technologies) was mounted on the machine in the back part, close the box for storing and transporting ore. This specific location was chosen based on our previous works, where it was proven that sensor placed closer to the box provides stronger indicators when the machine is performing ore unloading [25]. The sensor wasn't mounted on the box itself because: (1) the mounting case (designed to be placed horizontally) could not be simply converted to be mounted on the box, and (2) in such position there was a higher probability of damage. The sensor, along with its custom-made casing, installation method, and mounting locations is presented in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1. Setup used for data collection: A – Sensor, B – Casing of the sensor, C – Mounting place marked on haul truck [19].

The battery of the NGIMU sensor lasted for about 13 hours, which typically allowed for the recording of two full work shifts. The haul trucks used in this research operate on a four-shifts system, where work is performed in two-shifts blocks, after which the machines return to their assigned heavy machinery chamber. This setup allowed for the recording of 192 samples from a total of 20 different haul trucks, resulting in 2462 hours of recorded operation (primarily ore haulage).

The NGIMU device is essentially an IMU equipped with an onboard data logger (utilizing a micro SD card), a battery, and a Wi-Fi module. The IMU includes three 3-axis sensors: an accelerometer, a gyroscope, and a magnetometer. Additionally, the device can also measure temperature and humidity. The maximum sampling rate of the IMU sensors is 400 Hz; however, practical measurements showed this to be closer to 360 Hz. Initial experiments revealed that the magnetometer signals were unusable, likely due to interference from the steel casing and the underground mine environment. Consequently, the input features for the method presented in this paper are derived exclusively from the accelerometer and gyroscope readings. These features include linear acceleration (along longitudinal, lateral, and vertical axes) measured in units of (g), and angular velocity (along the same axes) measured in degrees per second (deg/s). Example raw signal waveforms of the IMU features, cropped to match the window width used by the algorithm, are shown in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. Raw signal waveforms used by the proposed method for cycles detection.

Each sample was categorized with the help of a specialized expert, who initially introduced eight operational classes, which were later reduced to five: (0) – Other, (1) – Driving

with a full box, (2) – Driving with an empty box, (3) – Unloading, and (4) – Loading. This reduction was necessary because some operations were indistinguishable from others based on their vibration characteristics, and distinguishing between them would require knowing what had been done earlier in the shift. Initial experiments showed that these five classes provide the best combination for cycle detection, which is consistent with previous work in this area.

Raw data preprocessing was limited to scaling each sensor’s data to the range $(-1, 1)$ using the maximum and minimum threshold values provided by the sensor manufacturer. Thus, gyroscope variables were scaled using a value of ± 2000 deg/s, and accelerometer variables were scaled using a value of ± 16 g.

B. PROPOSED METHOD FOR CYCLES DETECTION

The algorithm for detecting ore haulage cycles consists of several different techniques, due to the high complexity of both the data and the task. The general schema of these methods is shown in Fig. 3. Data from the IMU sensor mounted on the ore box are extracted using a windowing operation, and for each axis of the target sensors (accelerometer and gyroscope), the data are processed by unique encoders. The primary purpose of the encoders is to compress the information (reduce the data size while maintaining its quality) for easier processing by the neural network. The outputs from each encoder are concatenated and flattened, forming the input for the VGG16 model. The model estimates which class of operation the current window should be assigned to. After the entire sample has been processed, the assigned classes are compiled into one signal, which is then processed through three steps: first, it is cleaned by applying the machine operation schema; second, the cycles are detected; and third, validation procedures are performed on the detected cycles. The final output of this method is the number of detected cycles in a given signal sample (usually corresponding to one work shift).

FIGURE 3. General architecture of proposed method for cycles detection. (Blue) Procedures performed for each window of signal, (Green) Procedures performed for whole signal.

Before cycle detection begins, the sensor mounting operation should be removed from all signals. Since the machine is typically not used for some time after mounting, this task

FIGURE 4. Architecture of autoencoder that has been created and trained for each IMU sensor axis, model made in PyTorch.

FIGURE 5. Architecture of VGG16 model used in cycle detection method, model made in PyTorch.

usually involves removing all data recorded before the first long pause in the readings. This simple approach is suitable for the measurements used in this research; however, in other scenarios, alternative methods may be required. Therefore, we do not include this step as a formal part of the method.

The first procedure of the detection method is the windowing operation, which splits the signal into windows of 16384 samples (~45 seconds). Windows are shifted by 1/4th of the window length, resulting in a 75% overlap between consecutive windows. This overlap is necessary to ensure that no unloading operations are missed, as some can last less than 30 seconds. Each chunk (for each axis of each sensor) is then processed by the encoder model. The encoder was extracted from a convolutional autoencoder model, which was created and trained separately for each variable. The structure of the autoencoder model, written in PyTorch, is shown in Fig. 4. Autoencoders are a type of model that takes an input, transforms it into a smaller representation (in both size and dimensionality) called a latent representation, and then attempts to reconstruct the original input from this latent

vector (without the access to original input) [2]. Once each autoencoder was successfully trained—meaning the reconstructed signal was similar to the original, indicating a good latent representation—the encoder model was extracted and used for data compression in the initial stage. The output of each encoder has a shape of 8×512 (4096 flattened), representing a 4x reduction in size compared to the original sample.

Once the data from all sensors in the current window have been processed by their respective autoencoders, the outputs are flattened and concatenated. This operation transforms the encoder outputs, originally of shape $(6 \times 8 \times 512)$, into a single 1D vector with a length of 24576 values. This vector is then fed into the VGG16 model, which performs the classification task and assigns one of five classes. The structure of the model, written in PyTorch, is shown in Fig. 5. The VGG network is a well-known model typically used in various tasks, primarily involving image processing [20]. In this research, a slightly modified version was used: the convolutional layers were replaced with their 1D counterparts, along

with minor modifications to the strides to reduce the model size.

The aforementioned VGG network classifies each chunk into one of five possible categories. This marks the end of signal processing in chunks and the beginning of analyzing the signal as a whole. To do this, all chunks must first be extracted, processed, and classified. However, due to the overlap in the windowing operation and the presence of significant noise, the class vector must first be cleaned before detection can occur.

Cycle cleaning is performed on a 2D vector of size (4, X), where 4 corresponds to the fact that windows are shifted by 1/4th of their length (resulting in four unique windowing schemes), and X represents the total number of windows that can be generated: (signal length – initial shift) // window length. To merge these four different views of the data into one, the signal is first unfolded (repeated for the number of samples in the window), and then the views are aligned by shifting each vector so that the sample positions match in real time. Afterward, the algorithm iterates over each time point and assigns the most frequent operation (from up to four values) as the target for that moment. The only exception is when the unloading operation appears; in this case, it is assigned as the target, even if it shows up in only one of the four signals.

Once the vectors of possible operations are merged into one, a second stage of cleaning occurs, modifying the classification results based on the logical sequence of operations. In real-world operation, haul trucks typically follow a cycle: driving with an empty box, loading, driving with a full box, and unloading. Of course, additional operations may occur (as discussed in detail in [21], where haul truck operation is described as a state-based model), but these are categorized as “other.” Based on this schema, further cleaning is performed by enforcing a logic that checks transitions between two classes and overwrites the second class (by repeating the previous one) if it does not conform to the haul truck operation cycle. The allowed transitions are shown in Table 1. Additionally, the conditions account for situations where unloading was not detected, as this operation is the most difficult to detect using IMU sensor readings.

Based on the cleaned machine operation signal, two types of cycles are detected. The detection is performed using a pattern search, where the algorithm can identify either a proper cycle or a proposed cycle. The proposed cycle differs from the standard cycle by the absence of the unloading operation. Therefore, the proper cycle is defined as (1), while the proposed cycle is described as (2).

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \text{ Driving with full box} &> (3) \text{ Unloading} \\
 &> (2) \text{ Driving with empty box} \\
 &> (4) \text{ Loading} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \text{ Driving with full box} &> (2) \text{ Driving with empty box} \\
 &> (4) \text{ Loading} \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 1. Conditions used to clean signal of truck estimated operation.

Previous class	Current class	Comment
NOT Other (1, 2, 3, 4)	(0) Other	class other isn't useful for the cycles detection
(1) Driving with full box	NOT (2) Driving with empty box OR NOT (3) Unloading	if machine was already loaded, it cannot perform another loading
(2) Driving with empty box	NOT (4) Loading	when driving with empty box, machine can only be loaded
(3) Unloading	NOT (2) Driving with empty box	after unloading, machine can only drive with empty box
(4) Loading	NOT (1) Driving with full box	if machine was loaded it cannot drive with an empty box

The procedure described above is designed to minimize the cases where a cycle is performed but not detected by the algorithm (false negatives). This adjustment was made at the user’s request, as such situations escalate conflicts between operators and mine management. Consequently, the results from these actions often lead to false positives, which are subsequently reduced using a validation procedure.

Cycles performed by the machine during one shift should possess similar characteristics, as they are executed to and from the same locations throughout the entire shift. Changes in the locations of ore creation or mining faces are very rarely made, at least in large mining enterprises. Therefore, to reduce the increased number of false positives, the algorithm compares two main conditions between cycles performed by each machine during each shift. These conditions are:

- *Cycle time should be similar for every cycle during the shift*—cycle time is defined as the amount of time (in seconds) taken to perform every operation in either a proper cycle or a proposed cycle. To establish a baseline, the mean cycle time is calculated after applying the 1.5 IQR rule for cleaning. Any cycle that is shorter or longer by more than 100 % of the mean cycle time is flagged as a false positive.
- *The duration of driving with an empty box should be similar to that of driving with a full box*—typically, the machine follows the same route at similar speeds in both directions (after loading and after unloading). Therefore, for each cycle, these two durations are compared, and cycles where an imbalance is detected are flagged as false positives. The imbalance is defined as a difference greater than 150%.

The validation procedure allows for a considerable reduction in false positives with minimal impact on cycles that are true positives. This operation also concludes the method of cycle detection, the results of which are presented later in Section III.

C. MODELS TRAINING ROUTINE

The total number of neural network models used in this research is seven: six autoencoders and one VGG16 network. All of the autoencoders were trained in the same manner. The initial dataset was created by taking all of the IMU selected sensor readings and dividing them into chunks of duration equal to the input length (16,384 samples). These chunks were also used as the desired output for the autoencoder training. The graphs presenting the training loss and test validation function during each epoch for each encoder training are shown in Fig. 6. The following specifications were used during the training of each encoder:

- Dataset as whole consisted of 80 daily samples (each of around 12 hours duration)
- Overall training set size: $\sim 100\,000$
- Overall test size: $\sim 10\,000$
- Optimizer function: Adam, with $lr = 0.001$
- Loss function: Mean Squared Error
- Test validation function: Mean Absolute Percentage Error
- Epochs: 20

As can be seen, all encoders achieved a good representation of the initial data in the latent vector, as indicated by the test values showing less than 0.5 % error. Some examples of data processing performed by the autoencoders for accelerometers and gyroscopes are presented in Fig. 7. While only the latent representation is used in the method for cycle detection, there is a noticeable difference between the input and reconstructed signals. Primarily, the reconstruction helps to eliminate significant amounts of noise, which commonly occur with this type of sensor. Additionally, it is worth noting that other sizes of latent representation were tested, allowing for a 32-fold reduction in data size. However, due to the noticeable decrease in the quality of detecting the unloading operation, a 4-fold compression was established as the best choice.

Training the VGG model was a more sophisticated process and was conducted on the data first processed by the encoders. Additionally, the initial daily samples were verified by human experts to ensure that they consisted only of data of sufficient quality. As mentioned earlier, the input to the network was the flattened output from the six encoders, and the output was a class number (transformed with one-hot encoding) representing the operation performed during the chunk by the haul truck. The graph of the training process for the VGG16 model is presented in Fig. 8, and the following specifications were used during this process:

- Dataset as whole consisted of 46 daily samples (each of around 12 hours duration)
- Overall training set size: $\sim 78\,000$
- Overall test size: $\sim 7\,500$
- Optimizer function: Adam, with $lr = 0.001$ and $weight_decay = 0.00001$
- Loss function: Cross Entropy Loss
- Test validation function: Accuracy (multi-class)

- Epochs: Early Stopping Algorithm (monitoring test data validation function, threshold = 3% improvement)
- Learning Rate Scheduler: ReduceLROnPlateau (mode = 'min', factor = 0.2, patience = 5)
- Weighted Random Sampler used on train set

The figures mentioned above demonstrate that the network achieved a good accuracy of around 80%. As the final model, the one after the 9th epoch was selected because it showed the best results and was just before the onset of overfitting (indicated by an increase in accuracy for the training set and a decrease for the test set). For this model, a confusion matrix was created, which also indicated overall good classification results, with the most misleading class being (3) unloading. This was to be expected and is the reason why the model was not developed to operate independently from the start. After the entire signal is processed, the outputs from multiple runs of the VGG16 model are cleaned, resulting in a significant improvement over the original predictions.

III. RESULTS

An example of the predictions made by the method described in Section II is shown in Fig. 9, where the final signal after cleaning procedures is compared with the original human detection, as well as the raw output from the VGG16 model. It can be observed that the model's output bears some resemblance to reality; however, there is a significant amount of noise present. The final prediction (after cleaning) is almost identical to the human prediction, with minor differences in unloading and loading times. Nonetheless, these small differences do not significantly affect the main purpose of the method, which is to estimate the number of cycles performed during the measurement with the IMU sensor.

The proposed method was evaluated by comparing it to the previously mentioned human detection (which was also used to train all the models). From all the vibrational data gathered during underground experiments, the samples were divided into two categories. The first category ("Data used in train & validation" - 46 days, two shifts each) included data of very good quality, where cycles were clearly visible, and for the duration of two full shifts, the machine primarily performed ore haulage. The second category ("Other samples" - 77 days, usually two shifts each) included data of lesser quality, characterized by high levels of noise, sensor failures, and also some non-ore haulage work. The higher quality data group was used to train and validate the models (and the method), while the lower quality group was used to test the generalization capabilities of the proposed method. However, it is important to note that due to the much lower quality of the second group, a significant deterioration in the results is to be expected. The best indicator of data quality is the number of cycles detected in "Other samples" compared to the "Data used in training & validation". Despite having 1.6 times more data, the "Other samples" contain substantially fewer cycles (about 2.3 times less), highlighting lower data quality in these samples.

FIGURE 6. Training curves for autoencoders: (Red) – Mean Absolute Percentage Error (%) for test set, (Blue) – Mean Squared Error (loss function) for train set. The large variation in signals comes from the way of gathering given statistics (calculated per data chunk instead of per epoch).

FIGURE 7. Examples of data processing performed by autoencoders.

FIGURE 8. Training results for VGG16 model: A – accuracy for train and test data for each epoch (green line mark the model used in research), B – confusion matrix made from prediction for test data.

FIGURE 9. Example of detection result compared to raw VGG16 output and human detection.

The evaluation was performed by comparing the number of cycles detected in each sample using a confusion matrix (on a cycle basic, 1 TP = 1 wholly detected cycle). This process was carried out twice: first, for cycles that were detected with the unloading operation; second, for all cycles, regardless of whether unloading was detected. The evaluation metrics for the first group are presented in Table 2. The overall accuracy of cycle detection for the entire dataset is 82.13 %, which is considered suitable for industry applications. As mentioned, there is a noticeable drop in all metrics for samples of lesser quality. However, an accuracy above 70 % is still acceptable.

Unfortunately, there were a significant number of false negatives, which was not acceptable to the end user, hence the inclusion of cycles without detected unloading.

TABLE 2. Metrics for cycles detection.

Data Set	Train & validation			Other samples			All data		
Confusion Matrix	TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN
Cycles	890	5	134	374	61	75	1264	66	209
Accuracy [%]	86,49			73,33			82,13		
Recall [%]	86,91			83,30			85,81		
Precision [%]	99,44			85,98			95,04		
F1 Score [%]	92,76			84,62			90,19		

With the inclusion of cycles that do not have an unloading operation, all of the metrics showed improvement, except for precision. These results are presented in Table 3. Most importantly, the recall required by the end user increased to

95 %, along with a 5 % improvement in overall accuracy. The F1 score, which combines precision and recall, also improved, indicating that the trade-off was overall beneficial.

TABLE 3. Metrics for extended cycles detection.

Data Set	Train & validation			Other samples			All data		
Confusion Matrix	TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN
Cycles	978	17	46	431	116	18	1409	133	64
Accuracy [%]	93,95			76,28			87,73		
Recall [%]	95,51			95,99			95,66		
Precision [%]	98,29			78,79			91,37		
F1 Score [%]	96,88			86,55			93,47		

Given the current state of automatic work cycle detection, the achieved results can be considered successful, especially considering the experimental setup. Moreover, the end user was satisfied with the results, which indicates that the proposed method is sufficient for performing the intended task.

IV. CONCLUSION

Ore haulage is one of the most crucial processes performed in mines, and this is reflected in operational costs, especially for larger mines. Among the various means of ore transportation, tire machines, such as haul trucks and loaders, are the most popular due to their adaptability and ability to function in nearly any situation. While smaller mines rely solely on tire haulage, larger enterprises often use it in combination with other methods, such as conveyors, trains, and shafts. This makes efficiency monitoring particularly useful for

mining operations, as it can assist with optimization and cost reduction.

In this paper, we present an IMU-based method for efficiency monitoring dedicated to ore haulage by haul trucks. Our method is built on hundreds of hours of IMU data recorded in underground mines, collected from various machines in different locations (over 2,000 recorded work hours). The proposed method begins by using a set of encoders to compress readings from 3-axis accelerometers and gyroscopes, followed by the use of a VGG16 network to classify one of five possible work states for a haul truck: Unloading, Loading, Driving with an empty bucket, Driving with a full bucket, or Other. Since the initial estimation isn't perfect, a set of rules for cleaning and validation is applied, based on an analysis of haul truck operations. This allows the method to estimate a key performance indicator (KPI) that tracks the number of work cycles performed within a given time window.

The proposed method was validated, achieving an accuracy of 82.13 %, with a recall of 85.81 % and a precision of 95.04 %. To meet the end user's needs, the method was modified to minimize false negatives (cycles performed but not detected), resulting in improved accuracy (87.73 %) and recall (95.66 %), with a small reduction in precision (91.37 %). Given these metrics, it was concluded that the method is suitable for industrial implementation. While the results are not as high as those achieved by methods using variables from on-board measurement systems mounted by manufacturers, such as machine speed or engine rotation data, our approach offers a simple and easy to implement alternative that does not require extensive modifications to the machines. It can, therefore, be deployed in almost any scenario with minimal setup.

To the best of our knowledge, no existing methods for detecting haul truck cycles in underground mines utilize signals other than those captured by onboard machine monitoring systems mounted by machine producer. Such systems can be integrated during the machine assembly process and typically include a range of different sensors. For this specific task, the most important features identified in the literature are machine speed, engine rotation speed, and hydraulic system pressure, which controls the operation of the loading box. While such methods demonstrate slightly higher accuracies, achieving 90% [14] and 92.9% [22], the proposed approach offers a simpler, more portable solution that is easy to implement and requires neither extensive modifications to the machines nor the manufacturer's intervention. This method is particularly well-suited for scenarios where complex onboard measurement systems are unavailable.

While the achieved results are acceptable, there is room for improvement. No current method for work cycle detection in underground mines is both efficient and fully reliable, nor is there one that is easy to implement using technologies already in place. We believe future research should focus on exploring such methods, potentially involving other sensors or sensor fusion. Additionally, the proposed method was

tested in an industrial environment using an experimental setup. The sensors required charging before each working shift and were subsequently mounted on the machine by a technician. At the end of a two-shift block, the sensors were dismantled, and the data were manually downloaded from the SD card to a separate computer. The NGIMU sensors are equipped with capabilities for remote data transmission via Wi-Fi and can be connected to the machine's power supply. Therefore, implementing described procedure as an IoT solution represents a natural progression for further research. In such an implementation, the sensor could be powered directly by the machine, with data stored on the SD card and automatically uploaded whenever the machine is within range of strategically placed access points.

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